

VPP UNFRAMED DPP

Version 0

Description

The objective of the project is to create new knowledge on the factors and expressions of young people's (13-25 years old) participation, its authenticity in formal and non-formal education settings, as well as in extracurricular activities; develop strategies and practical solutions for the promotion of authentic and meaningful participation both on individual level and in the interaction of involved stakeholders; make an epistemological and practical contribution to the development of a youth-centred participatory approach.

A methodology in which the boundary between researchers, educators and young people is made permeable has been chosen: design-based implementation research, participatory action research, and participatory evaluation research. Visual methods, including digital storytelling and photovoice, will be used to explore young people's experiences. The research project will be implemented by the Latvian Academy of Culture and its interdisciplinary researchers' team experienced in research on democratic and participatory processes, as well as on the youth sector. Testing and validating new forms of civic participation will contribute to an open and democratic learning environment. Apart from scientific publications, a range of applied results are planned aimed at recommendations for youth and education policy makers. The impact of the project is planned on the field of education sciences, as well as youth sociology, and their research community in Latvia and abroad.

Funder

Ministry of Education and
Science, Republic of Latvia

Grant

The State Research
Programme 'Education'
(2023-2026)

Researchers

Liene Valdmane, Sabīne Ozola, Anda Laķe (orcid:0000-0002-1472-0813), Līga Vinogradova (orcid:0000-0002-7519-5450),
Baiba Tjarve (orcid:0000-0003-0770-3377), Gints Klāsons
(orcid:0000-0002-2979-5463)

Organizations

Latvian Academy of Culture

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [VPP UNFRAMED DPP](#)

Description:

The objective of the project is to create new knowledge on the factors and expressions of young people's (13-25 years old) participation, its authenticity in formal and non-formal education settings, as well as in extracurricular activities; develop strategies and practical solutions for the promotion of authentic and meaningful participation both on individual level and in the interaction of involved stakeholders; make an epistemological and practical contribution to the development of a youth-centred participatory approach.

A methodology in which the boundary between researchers, educators and young people is made permeable has been chosen: design-based implementation research, participatory action research, and participatory evaluation research. Visual methods, including digital storytelling and photovoice, will be used to explore young people's experiences. The research project will be implemented by the Latvian Academy of Culture and its interdisciplinary researchers' team experienced in research on democratic and participatory processes, as well as on the youth sector. Testing and validating new forms of civic participation will contribute to an open and democratic learning environment. Apart from scientific publications, a range of applied results are planned aimed at recommendations for youth and education policy makers. The impact of the project is planned on the field of education sciences, as well as youth sociology, and their research community in Latvia and abroad.

Researchers:

[Liene Valdmane](#)

[Sabīne Ozola](#)

[Anda Laķe \(orcid:0000-0002-1472-0813\)](#)

[Līga Vinogradova \(orcid:0000-0002-7519-5450\)](#)

[Baiba Tjarve \(orcid:0000-0003-0770-3377\)](#)

[Gints Klāsons \(orcid:0000-0002-2979-5463\)](#)

Organizations:

[Latvian Academy of Culture](#)

Contact: [Ance Kristāla](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Ministry of Education and Science, Republic of Latvia](#)

Grants: [The State Research Programme 'Education' \(2023-2026\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2024-06-20](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Survey data obtained in the project on the prerequisites for civic participation of young people (13-25 years) and the dominant forms of civic participation in formal education settings, non-formal education settings and outside education settings.

The data collection method is a analytical cross-sectional quantitative survey among young people aged 13-25 who study in formal and non-formal secondary and higher education institutions in Latvia.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To obtain and analyse empirical data on the prerequisites for civic participation of young people (13-25 years) and the dominant forms of civic participation in

formal education settings, non-formal education settings and outside education settings (a quantitative survey will be conducted among young people aged 13-25 who study in formal and non-formal secondary and higher education institutions in Latvia. The planned sample size is approximately 1000. Data will be analysed in IBM SPSS Statistics, with the aim of identifying correlations between education level, type of educational institution (formal/non-formal), age group of young people, fields of interest education and preconditions for civic participation, dominant forms of civic participation, and signs/indicators of authentic and meaningful civic participation)

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- csv
- sav

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

This type of data has not been collected before

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in youth sociology, civic participation and other social scientists

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Anonymized survey data will be published in open access repository Zenodo and can be used by third parties, indicating the origin of the data. Where appropriate (in relation to data-protection issues), researchers will upload files comprising raw data for sharing and reuse by academic and stakeholder communities.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repository is managed by CERN, ensuring lifetime access as well as data security

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPPS or similar

SPSS

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

CSV and SAV formats

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Internationally recognised licence, applicable to data produced within the scope of national research programmes

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-21

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))
- Ance Kristāla (orcid: [0000-0003-0644-3737](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0644-3737))

The project coordinator is responsible for data handling, and the data management officer is responsible for deposition

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Any work with minors will be subject to clearance and informed consent from parents and guardians.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Survey data obtained in the project on the formal and non-formal educational environment as an institutional framework for civic participation (including decision-making, trust).

The data collection method is a quantitative online survey among representatives of student self-governments in educational institutions (pupils and students) and youth councils at the municipalities.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To obtain and analyse empirical data on the prerequisites for civic participation of young people (13-25 years) and the dominant forms of civic participation in formal education settings, non-formal education settings and outside education settings (a quantitative survey will be conducted among young people aged 13-25 who study in formal and non-formal secondary and higher education institutions in Latvia. The planned sample size is approximately 1000. Data will be analysed in IBM SPSS Statistics, with the aim of identifying correlations between education level, type of educational institution (formal/non-formal), age group of young people, fields of interest education and preconditions for civic participation, dominant forms of civic participation, and signs/indicators of authentic and meaningful civic participation)

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- csv
- sav

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

This type of data has not been collected before

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in youth sociology, civic participation and other social scientists

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Anonymized survey data will be published in open access repository Zenodo and can be used by third parties, indicating the origin of the data. Where appropriate (in relation to data-protection issues), researchers will upload files comprising raw data for sharing and reuse by academic and stakeholder communities.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repository is managed by CERN, ensuring lifetime access as well as data security

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPPS or similar

SPSS

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

CSV and SAV formats

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Internationally recognised licence, applicable to data produced within the scope of national research programmes

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-21

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))
- Ance Kristāla (orcid: [0000-0003-0644-3737](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0644-3737))

The project coordinator is responsible for data handling, and the data management officer is responsible for deposition

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Online surveys will include a consent form for publishing data in an open archive

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

